

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: Wright****FIRST NAME: Skeeter****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**The author applied US XUK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Windows 10

ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

My initial impression of the ACA-401D assignment was one of confusion. It was my understanding that a person with substantial academic and professional background may be assumed to be capable of writing an essay or a paper in a prescribed format and style. Upon later reflection, I realized that an effective way to learn a format and aspects related to authoring a paper for a particular audience or purpose is to write a paper describing the prescribed matters. Further to that, the course provided reference material of which I had no knowledge. The reference material will be helpful when I write papers for other audiences or purposes such as scientific journals or governments.

2) PERIOD 1 INFORMATION

The information available via Euclid University's ACA-401 Coursepack includes a document from the University of New South Wales titled "Essay Writing, The Basics" which presents logical steps that lead to the formulation of an approach to writing and then writing an academic paper (EUCLID 2015, 1-4).

Scientific and academic papers are often a response to a question, a proposed approach to answering a question or a critique of someone's response or proposed approach. In each case, following the steps outlined in the "Essay Writing, The Basics" (Ibid.) provides an understanding of the matter at hand and a means by which to develop and adjust one's approach to the matter to be written about.

Undertaking research of the matter provides the background upon which a thesis or perspective is formed. An important part of the research is identifying credible sources of information. This sometimes entails researching the sources. Notes of the researched information provide a summary of the information and a quick check later on aspects of the essay's outline.

An essay's plan or outline provides the basics to be described and elaborated upon in the essay. The first draft of an essay may be considered a test of the logic and content that is refined in a subsequent draft. The University of New South Wales paper suggests stepping away from the essay for a day to two, so to gain a fresh perspective on the approach and information in draft one (Ibid.). Draft two may consist of minor edits or even a new approach to the essay. Having a friend or colleague read the draft is also suggested. Completing the essay, checking the references and completing the bibliography are followed by submitting the essay.

Another source of information provided is "Initial Student Orientation 2019". It provides information about and access to Grammarly which is writing assistance software (EUCLID 2019, 3). Grammarly's real-time grammar and spell checking reduces later edits, therefore expediting corrections. It provides authoritative information on simple, yet important grammar matters such as the use of commas, hyphens, and proper possessive punctuation.

Also included in "Initial Student Orientation 2019" is a link to Bennet College's document "Turabian Style: Footnotes/Endnotes & Bibliography" (Ibid.). It provides easily understood information on noting references and citations in footnotes, endnotes, and a bibliography. A second Bennet College document, "Turabian Style: In-Text (Parenthetical) Citations & Reference List" (Ibid.) as well as the first Bennet College document, provides information and examples of appropriate styles for a plethora of written works.

Access to Grammarly and Turabian would have greatly reduced the time and effort I previously expended in writing papers for academia, governments, and scientific journals. Instead of searching for style guides and then checking their applicability to the task at hand, real-time access to Grammarly and Turabian would have freed time for other important work. Contrary to the generally accepted writing styles of scientific journals and governments' analysis papers, the Euclid student is to write in an interactive and personal style as a response paper (EUCLID 2019, 4).

I have found some journals prescribe the format to be used for submissions, including the font type and size, indented paragraphs or not, spacing between paragraphs and the maximum number of words. The "Initial Student Orientation 2019" notes the importance of adhering to the prescribed form. Word is the required text software, with the Title style used only once for the main title followed by the Normal style for the text. Headings fall with three categories. Top-level titles, followed by subtitles, followed by sub subtitles as needed. Running citations are placed in a separate paragraph. The body of the document is followed by the bibliography which uses the Bibliography style format (EUCLID 2019, 2-3).

Other information in “Initial Student Orientation 2019” refers to the importance of citing sources of information and the total lack of tolerance for plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 4). Plagiarism may take two forms. Plagiarism may occur when another person’s work is paraphrased, and no credit given to the source. Plagiarism also occurs when parts or the whole of another person’s work is provided with the intent to claim it as one’s own. I recall that in an undergrad tutorial the instructor noted a journal article we were discussing included plagiarized sections. The author had claimed responsibility for ideas that the instructor knew had originated in an article in a different journal by a different author.

A third source of information is Euclid University’s document in the ACA-401 Coursepack on an ideal paper (EUCLID. 2015. 5-41). It provides a succinct, point form collection of salient information on a well-written paper. Further to that, the extensive information about plagiarism (EUCLID 2015, 7-12) highlights the importance of providing appropriate credit to sources, not explicitly or via implication leaving the reader with misinformation as to the source of an idea or the text.

The “Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers” in the ACA-401 Coursepack (EUCLID 2015, 42-44) is very useful as a quick guide to the basics. It is an easy to use, to the point document one may use after reading and absorbing more extensive descriptions of the salient points.

One particular point, clarity of writing, is what one may assume is a given in any written work. Unfortunately, clarity is sometimes lacking in some papers I have read. It also was lacking in some papers I have written. Occasionally, the clarity in my work has been improved by my leaving the paper for a day or two and coming back to it with a fresh perspective or by my asking someone not directly familiar with the subject to read it. Clarity in writing may be achieved for an audience with limited knowledge of the subject and related background by briefly noting the relevant background. However, when writing for an audience with substantial knowledge of and background in the subject, one may justly assume less information is needed for the reader to draw the desired linkages and conclusions.

It is important to identify the audience of a paper. By doing so, one has an idea of the background knowledge of the reader. This allows for less detailed explanations of some points in the paper and identifies where more detail would be helpful. When writing for a subject-specific scientific journal, an assumption is made that the readers have a background in the subject and may be aware of recent developments in the field. However, it is still important to cite sources of information when describing matters not yet considered common knowledge in the field or more importantly recent perspectives or discoveries in that subject’s field.

A PowerPoint presentation is included in the ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1. Unfortunately, I was not able to use whatever was in the presentation. My home is off-grid, in that I generate my electricity, have wood heat and rely on a nearby stream for water. Also, I have very limited access to the internet in that my only connection to a distant transmission tower is sporadic and quite slow. Therefore, I have yet to successfully download the PowerPoint presentation.

3) CONCLUSION

Upon reflecting on my initial thoughts about the ACA-401 Course Pack, Period 1, I realized that my confusion was generated by not yet being acquainted with the material. Further to that, I later found that the information provided is helpful even to someone with my extensive background in preparing papers for governments, boards of directors and students. The information and suggested techniques served in some cases as a reminder and in others as a new approach. Information on how to cite sources for different types of publications, the assistance with grammar, and suggestions on how to approach a written assignment are appreciated and will serve me well in both my studies at Euclid University and my profession.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack Period 1*. <https://eucliduniversity.net/periods/aca-401-period-1> (accessed on 8th February 2020).

Euclid University. 2019. *Initial Student Orientation 2019*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

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